

THE FOUNDATION OF CULTURAL LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: This article defines cultural linguistics, its directions and the notion of the concept. A interdisciplinary field of study called "cultural linguistics" investigates how language and cultural conceptions interact. The field of Cultural Linguistics has expanded its theoretical foundation in recent times, especially with regard to the concept of cultural cognition, by incorporating several fields and sub-disciplines including distributed cognition and complexity science. Furthermore, it discusses the multidimensional nature of concepts, integrating perspectives from cognitive and cultural linguistics. By elucidating the interplay between linguistic choices, mental processes, and cultural contexts, this paper underscores the holistic approach of cognitive linguistics in unraveling the intricate tapestry of human language and cognition

Keywords: Cultural Linguistics, culture, language, approaches, meaning, Concept, cognitive grammar, cognitive semantics, thought, linguistic theory, multidisciplinary approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cognitive linguistics is a modern, actively developing scientific research is the field. Cognitive linguistics is the science of human cognition, this is recognized as one of the central areas of cognitology. Cognitive term derived from the English word "cognitive" and from Latin and Greek. It is related to the concepts of knowledge, understanding, thinking. Knowledge of the world, reality, perception, reflection in mind and language, communication through language, transmission and reception of information is not a simple phenomenon.

Cognitive linguistics in philosophy not limited to the theory of knowledge, but connecting language with thinking and its creation psychological, biological and neurophysiological aspects of social, cultural, makes a deep scientific study of its organic connection with linguistic phenomena. American psychologist H. Gardner at the intersection of cognitive sciences, six disciplines (philosophy, psychology, Linguistics, anthropology, artificial intelligence, neurology) and the only one scientific goal - accumulation, processing of knowledge in natural and artificial systems and He noted that he would be busy looking for a solution to the problems of its application (Gardner 1987) [1].

Moreover, it needs to clarify that Cognitive linguistics is a new branch of linguistics. Cognitive linguistics emerged in the 1970s through the work of researchers who studied the relationship between language and thought. They did not choose the direction of studying the internal and special structural structure

of the language that was dominant at that time. Rather than distinguishing syntax from other parts of language in the syntactic component, which is governed by a set of several principles and elements, cognitive laws and mechanisms that are not relevant for language, including: human differentiation, practical and the laws of interaction and the laws of task in general, imagery and economics.

2 METHODS

Linguists who contributed the most to the development of cognitive linguistics and did the most work in this field: Wallace Chafe, Charles Fillmore, George Lakoff, Ronald Langacker, Leonard Talmy.[2] All these linguists approached their linguistic theories based on a certain set of phenomena and concepts. All the scientists mentioned above put forward one hypothesis. Meaning is so important in language that it should be the main focus in the learning process. These views were opposed to those of the Chomsky school of linguists, who viewed meaning as interpretive and secondary [3]. Syntax was the most important object of research for them.

Thinking is the process by which knowledge is acquired. It includes perception, intuition, logic. That is why cognitive linguistics is related to psychology, neuropsychology and other disciplines. The most basic unit for cognitive linguistics is the concept. In the process of language-related actions, people reveal their knowledge about different fields, the world and people. This, in turn, makes it easier for our thinking to categorize all the information we have. Major categories of thought include space and time, being and process,

action and location, cause and effect, desire and desire. Different mechanisms were used to make this knowledge easier to remember and apply. However, language does not always convey the same meaning in different situations, that is, meaning is expressed in different ways depending on the sources of thought.

This Cognitive Linguistics has developed in different directions: cognitive grammar, cognitive stylistics, cognitive semantics, gender linguistics, ethnolinguistics, cognitive phonetics. Among them, cognitive grammar and cognitive semantics are of particular importance.

The term cognitive grammar has two meanings. In a broad sense, cognitive grammar is synonymous with cognitive linguistics. It is manifested in language cognitive activities such as: memory, perception, attention and thinking. In the narrow sense, cognitive grammar is a branch of cognitive linguistics. Talmy and Langacker are the most famous in the origin of cognitive grammar.

Psycholinguists are the scientists who first studied Cognitive Semantics - Cognitive Linguistics. In their studies, they proved the existence of non-verbal thinking and also argued about the existence or non-existence of a conceptual system in the human brain. A conceptual system consists of ever-changing and evolving concepts.

Scientists have concluded that symbols are created by humans and emphasize that they serve to deliver the most important information. But, in their view, the conceptual system is larger and only a small part of it is represented by symbols. According to R. M. Frumkina, cognitive semantics is inextricably linked with cognitive psychology [4]. Cognitive semantics defines or expresses the meaning of language based on how it is reflected in the human brain. Unlike traditional semantics, cognitive semantics studies linguistic events based on extra-linguistic factors, that is, mainly psychological and socio-cultural factors.

One of the scientists who made a great contribution to cognitive semantics as a science is A. Wierzbicka. He argues that while studying symbols, we can study a person's conceptual system and understand what period is important to him[5]. As mentioned above, such concepts are a non-verbal reflection of the human thought process and are understood with the help of symbols. According to the theory of cognitive semantics, language is a container and a collection of knowledge in the human brain. Language reflects human quality. Therefore, cognitive semantics does not exclude pragmatics. Cognitive semantics divides meaning into two main units, meaning structure and knowledge reflection. According to scientists, meaning

is conceptual, that is, It is related to the representation of something in the real world.

On the contrary, it can also be related to an object or an idea in the human brain. That is, one thing cannot be understood in the same way by people. It should be noted that understanding the meaning depends on the speaker's personal experience. Meanings can be expressed and implied correctly, incorrectly, clearly and vaguely. Cognitive linguistics studies these things.

2.1 The notion of the concept

Consequently, cognitive linguistics is concerned with the study of the relationships between linguistics choices and mental processes, human experience and its results - knowledge. Cognitive linguistics regards language as a cognitive mechanism of representing, storing and transferring knowledge layers. In the domain of cognitive linguistics there have been distinguished as mentioned above different trends and approaches. To sum up above theories, it needs to be stressed again that the cognitive approach connects into all aspects of linguistic theory: cognitive semantics, cognitive grammar, cognitive phonetics, cognitive stylistics and cognitive pragmatics.

One of the main notions of Cognitive linguistics is the notion of the concept. At present the notion of concept is in the center of attention of many modern linguistic trends such as cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology, linguoconceptology, etc.

3 DISCUSSION

Concept is characterized as a multiple mental structure comprising of notional, image-bearing, and evaluative constituents. examinations consideration is centered on the issues of the concept structure, the ways of its verbalization on various levels of the dialect framework. As V.A Maslova claims, the arrangement of a concept is conditioned by the individual's passionate, physical, chronicled, individual and social involvement procured within the handle of the world recognition[6]. The taking after characteristics of a concept pertinent for the anecdotal content and its elucidation can be laid out concept presents information structures around the surrounding world; concept could be a social and broadly particular unit; concept may be a multiple mental structure comprising of notional, picture bearing and evaluative constituents; concept is characterized by a string of passionate, expressive components and affiliated joins.

There are two approaches to this problem: cognitive and cultural. From the positions of cognitive linguistics "concept" is considered a complex mental unit, means of representation of knowledge structures, multifold cognitive structure, an operational unit of memory (Kubryakova E.S., Demyankov V.Z., Boldirev N.N.,

Alefirenko N.F., Sternin I.A.)[7]. From the perspectives of linguoculturology "concept" is defined as a mental, cultural and nationally specific unit characterized by an array of emotional, expressive and evaluative components, as a basic unit of culture, a constituent part of the national conceptsphere (Stepanov Yu.S., Arutyunova N.D., Karasik V.I., Slisshkin G.G., Vorkachyov S.G., Pimenova M.V.)[8].

Despite some differences in approaches, as V.I. Karasik points out, the "linguocultural and cognitive approaches to the notion of concept are not mutually exclusive: concept as a mental unit in the mind of the individual provides access to the concept sphere of the society, while the cultural concept is a unit of the collective cultural experience, which becomes the cultural property of the individual [Karasik, 2004:135][9].

One of the most important tasks in the concept theory is the study of its structure. There are different views and approaches to this problem.

Yu. S. Stepanov outlines a "layered" structure of the concept distinguishing: a) the main (current, known to each carrier of culture); b) additional (passive, historical relevant to the individual carriers of culture), and c) inner content known only to special investigators (Stepanov, 2004)[10].

R.M. Frumkina distinguishes: a) the core (the conceptual characteristics that identify a concept), and b) the periphery, (pragmatic, associative, connotative, figurative, expressive features of the concept (Rumkina, 1996).

But most researchers such as V.I. Karasik, G. Slisshkin, S.G. Vorkachyov, Z.D. Popova, LA Sternin and others assert that "concept" is composed of three constituents [11]:

- 1) notional (factual information, i.e. the basic, essential and distinctive features of the concept);
- 2) imagery (based on the principle of analogy);
- 3) evaluative (axiological and cultural significance).

The researchers define the concept's linguistic fixation—its definition and interpretation of its elements and their structures, as well as its comparative characteristics with respect to other concepts—by notional component. An overall perception of a certain thing, phenomenon, or event associated with a particular circumstance and stored in human memory is known as an image-bearing component. Lastly, the evaluation component requires the whole of concepts (because a concept cannot exist in isolation from other concepts) examined within the framework of values that constitute the evaluation worldview. The most fundamental senses, or evaluative dominants, are identified in this

intricate mental basis, creating a particular kind of culture that is preserved in the language.

One characteristic that sets the concept apart is its interlevel nature, meaning that ideas are expressed using a variety of language units that pertain to distinct language levels, such as lexical, word-formation, phraseological, syntactical, and paremiologically. However, a thorough reconstruction, actualization, and decoding of the semantic and cultural structure of the notion can only be reached on the textual level, according to several linguists (Kubryakova E.S., Ashurova D.U., Maslova V.A.)[12]. The text's concept is emphasized by a number of linguistic units, the examination of which, in the context of concept theory, enables a deeper understanding of the text's underlying meaning.

In this way, the cognitive linguistics defines the concept as a mental unit reflecting the reality, which is formed by the conceptualization of objects and phenomena in the surrounding world. In other words, concepts are «quanta» of knowledge, experience and the results of human activities. While linguoculturology considers a concept as a mental unit which is marked to some extent with ethno-semantically specific elements. While the aggregate of cognitive concepts form the conceptual structure (concept sphere) as a fully established semantic foundation, the cultural concepts occupy certain space in making each ethnic group culturally unique.

3 CONCLUSIONS

As a conclusion, central to cognitive linguistics is the concept of the concept, which serves as a fundamental unit of human cognition and culture. Scholars approach the study of concepts from cognitive and cultural perspectives, recognizing their role in representing knowledge structures and shaping cultural identity. The article also delves into the structure of concepts, outlining their notional, image-bearing, and evaluative constituents, and emphasizing their interlevel character within language.

In summary, cognitive linguistics offers a multidisciplinary framework for understanding the complex interplay between language, cognition, and culture. By investigating the cognitive mechanisms underlying language use and meaning construction, cognitive linguistics enriches our understanding of human thought and communication.

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